

Determination of EMI Shielding Efficiency of Graphene Composites with Silver Nanoparticles Prepared Under Low-dose Gamma Irradiation

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Graphene and its derivatives (graphene oxide - GO and reduced graphene oxide - rGO) have high surface area and therefore are great materials to anchor metallic nanoparticles. The oxygen-containing groups in the GO structure serve as locations where metal nanoparticles can be anchored. Amongst various potential applications, silver nanostructures are widely studied for electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding applications due to their high electrical conductivity and high aspect ratio. Here, we prepared silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs) by low-dose (1-20 kGy) gamma irradiation of silver nitrate in the presence of graphene-based material (GO or electrochemically exfoliated graphene - EEG). By selecting this experimental procedure we opted for the pathway that does not require harsh chemicals and excessive purification steps, making it cost-efficient and environmentally friendly, and by using graphene sheets for the nucleation and growth of silver nanoparticles we made the use of a capping agent superfluous. The obtained Ag NPs were spherical with a predominant size distribution of 10-50 nm for GO and 10-100 nm for EEG and uniformly distributed over graphene sheets. EMI shielding efficiency measurements showed poor EMI shielding for the composites prepared with GO. On the other hand, all composites prepared with EEG showed EMI shielding to some extent, and the best performance was measured for the samples prepared at 5 and 20 kGy doses.

01 INTRODUCTION

Graphene has become a rising star of 2D nanomaterials due to its exceptional physicochemical characteristics, such as high surface area, low density, outstanding electrical conductivity, thermal stability, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility. In addition to its original features, graphene's surface modification can provide additional functions and expand its applications. To make graphene more water-dispersible, strong oxidants are often used to covalently modify graphene to produce graphene oxide (GO) whose functional groups at the surface serve as strong anchoring sites for the **nucleation and growth of metal nanoparticles**. By growing these nanoparticles directly on graphene, the presence of a stabilizing (capping) agent is redundant. Graphene sheets prevent the overgrowth or agglomeration of nanoparticles and ensure their long-term stability.

03 DISCUSSION

- ⁶⁰Co nuclide provides sufficient energy to cause the **radiolysis of water** and the emergence of **reactive oxidative and reductive species**.
- The primary reductive species that originate from the radiolysis of water such as **hydrated electron** ($e^-_{(aq)}$) and **hydrogen radical** (H^\cdot) have standard potentials of -2.9 V versus standard hydrogen electrode (SHE) and -2.4 V/SHE, respectively.
- The introduction of isopropyl alcohol that acts as a **scavenger of oxidative species** helps in creating the predominately reductive environment, transforming the isopropanol molecule into a secondary radical α -methyl-hydroxyethyl radical.
- Both primary and secondary species can **reduce silver ions to a zero valent state** considering that the standard redox potential for Ag^+/Ag is 0.7996 V/SHE.
- The **presence of oxygen moieties** on graphene's structure is responsible for the **nucleation and growth of Ag nanoparticles**, as well as for their stabilization after growth.
- It is speculated that **carboxyl and carbonyl groups** are predominantly localized **at the edges of sheets** on sp^2 hybridized C atoms, while **hydroxyl and epoxy groups** are placed **on the basal plane** on sp^3 hybridized carbon.
- Gamma irradiation simultaneously causes the reduction of graphene oxide and **partial restoration of sp^2 graphene's conjugated structure**.

05 CONCLUSIONS

We employed low-dose gamma irradiation (1–20 kGy) to prepare nanocomposites of silver nanoparticles anchored to two types of graphene-based materials: graphene oxide and electrochemically exfoliated graphene. The prepared Ag nanoparticles were spherical and homogeneously distributed onto the graphene sheets. Their predominant size distribution was 10–50 nm for graphene oxide and 10–100 nm for electrochemically exfoliated graphene. EEG/Ag NPs composites showed improved EMI shielding properties compared to their GO counterparts.

02 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of starting materials

As a starting graphene material, we used **graphene oxide (GO)** obtained by modified Hummers' method and **electrochemically exfoliated graphene (EEG)** obtained by electrochemical exfoliation. GO was prepared by mixing graphite powder with concentrated sulfuric acid and sodium nitrate at 0°C . Then, potassium permanganate was added while the solution was continuously stirred in a water bath to keep the temperature below 20°C . After 30 min of stirring, 100 mL of distilled water was added, after which the temperature was raised to 98°C and maintained for 2 h. After that time, the reaction mixture was diluted with 400 mL of water and 30% hydrogen peroxide was added before allowing the liquid to cool down to room temperature. EEG was prepared in a two-electrode system using highly oriented pyrolytic graphite rods as both the counter and the working electrode. Ammonium persulfate solution was used as an electrolyte. A direct current (DC) voltage of $+12$ V was applied, and the voltage was kept constant until the exfoliation process was finished, which was indicated by the total consumption of the working electrode.

Preparation of graphene composites with silver nanoparticles

Silver nitrate was added to the water dispersion of graphene (GO or EEG) to set an $AgNO_3$ concentration of 0.001 M. Then, isopropyl alcohol was added to the reaction mixture in a volume ratio of 1:10. Additionally, argon was purged through the reaction mixture before irradiation for 15 min to remove dissolved oxygen. The vials were then hermetically sealed and **exposed to gamma radiation**. Gamma-ray flux from the ^{60}Co nuclide was used for the irradiations, with a dose rate of 8.8 kGy/h. Samples were exposed to the gamma irradiation source, **receiving 1, 5, 10, and 20 kGy doses**.

04 RESULTS

SEM image and EDS maps of the corresponding area for carbon, oxygen, and silver for (a) GO, (b) GO/Ag NP prepared at 5 kGy, (c) GO/Ag NP prepared at 20 kGy, (d) EEG, (e) EEG/Ag NP prepared at 5 kGy, and (f) EEG/Ag NP prepared at 20 kGy.

FTIR spectra of (a) GO (reference) and GO/Ag NP composite irradiated at 20 kGy and (b) EEG (reference) and EEG/Ag NP composite irradiated at 20 kGy.

Both GO and EEG show similar absorption bands that can be attributed to various oxygen-containing functional moieties on the graphene's surface. After the irradiation, in the spectrum of GO/Ag NPs, bands from stretching vibrations of hydroxyl or carboxyl groups, and stretching vibrations of C-O groups are not detectable, while the band from carbonyl groups has decreased intensity. On the other hand, the spectrum of EEG/Ag NPs shows the same bands as the starting EEG. This might be an indication of a better susceptibility to the reduction of GO under gamma-ray flux in comparison to EEG.

UV-Vis spectra of (a) GO (reference) and GO/Ag NPs prepared at different irradiation doses and (b) EEG (reference) and EEG/Ag NPs prepared at different irradiation doses.

TEM images of (a) GO/Ag NPs prepared at 1 kGy irradiation dose, (b) GO/Ag NPs prepared at 20 kGy irradiation dose, (c) particle size distribution for GO/Ag NPs, (d) TEM images of EEG/Ag NPs prepared at 1 kGy irradiation dose, (e) EEG/Ag NPs prepared at 20 kGy irradiation dose and (f) particle size distribution for EEG/Ag NPs.

TEM provides Z-contrast images which enable a clear distinction between Ag ($Z = 47$) that appears as dark spots compared to pale gray areas of C ($Z = 6$). For both GO and EEG, the obtained Ag nanoparticles are predominantly spherical and uniformly cover the surface of graphene sheets. For GO, the majority of obtained Ag nanoparticles ($\sim 75\%$) have sizes between 10 and 50 nm, while for the applied dose of 20 kGy, we noticed only a minor increase in the 50–100 nm particle size range and a decrease in big particles (> 100 nm). On the other hand, only 45% of Ag nanoparticles prepared on EEG have sizes between 10 and 50 nm and a significant portion of Ag nanoparticles is larger. This dissimilarity in Ag nanoparticle size distribution might be due to the difference in the number of oxygen-containing functional groups between GO and EEG. Additionally, for EEG, a considerable increase in 50–100 nm particles and a decrease in > 100 nm particles could be noticed after the 20 kGy dose irradiation.

SEM-EDS analyses were performed to explore the distribution of the constituent elements of the prepared composites. In the starting graphene materials (GO and EEG), we detected only C and O with traces amount of sulfur and sodium that remained from the synthetic procedure. Elemental analysis showed that GO has a higher O content than EEG. All composites of GO and EEG showed homogeneous coverage of graphene sheets by Ag nanoparticles.

TGA curves of (a) GO (reference) and GO/Ag NPs prepared at different irradiation doses and (b) EEG (reference) and EEG/Ag NPs prepared at different irradiation doses.

GO has a greater portion of thermally labile oxygen-containing groups compared to EEG. For both GO and EEG weight loss is most prominent for non-irradiated samples, and with the increase in the irradiation dose, this weight loss gradually decreases. This is an indication of the partial restoration of graphene's conjugated structure and the elimination of oxygen-containing functionalities caused by the reduction under gamma irradiation.

EMI shielding efficiency measurements. (a) S_{21} amplitude of GO and GO/Ag NPs composites, and (b) S_{21} amplitude of EEG and EEG/Ag NPs composites.

The spectrum of GO displays two different features: a strong peak from the aromatic C=C bonds' $\pi-\pi^*$ transition, and a shoulder from the C-O bonds' $n-\pi^*$ transition, while the spectrum of EEG shows only $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of aromatic C=C bonds. The peak from the aromatic C=C bonds shows a gradual redshift with the increase in the irradiation dose, while the shoulder at ~ 300 nm in the GO/Ag NPs samples gradually decreases until it completely vanishes at the higher applied doses of 10 and 20 kGy. Additionally, the LSPR peak from Ag nanoparticles appears as one broad peak at ~ 420 nm.

Elemental composition of GO, EEG, and their composites with Ag nanoparticles prepared at different irradiation

Sample	Wt.%			Sample	Wt.%		
	C	O	Ag		C	O	Ag
GO	70.9	29.1	-	EEG	76.7	23.3	-
GO/Ag NP 1 kGy	62.6	28.7	8.7	EEG/Ag NP 1 kGy	84.9	14.3	0.8
GO/Ag NP 5 kGy	63.0	29.0	8.0	EEG/Ag NP 5 kGy	82.5	13.0	4.5
GO/Ag NP 10 kGy	66.6	25.8	13.6	EEG/Ag NP 10 kGy	74.4	16.9	8.7
GO/Ag NP 20 kGy	63.3	21.9	14.8	EEG/Ag NP 20 kGy	78.0	15.2	8.8

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